

**INVESTIGATING NON-ENGLISH MAJOR STUDENTS' (IPER) NEEDS, ATTITUDES,
AND ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING WAYS****Yuldasheva Saodat Khalmurzayevna****PhD, docent, “International school of finance technology and science”****Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich****Senior Teacher, “International school of finance technology and science”****Abstract**

Students learn English with different educational backgrounds at institute level. Through this course, students can get the opportunity to develop their English competence for their learning success and future professional needs. To maximize the attainments of the goals, ESP teachers need to design ESP courses relevant to the students' needs and conditions. This study surveyed 200 non-English major students (IPER institute) to investigate their needs in learning English, learning attitude, and language learning strategies. The results reveal students still lacking in all English skills and language use. Therefore, ESP teachers should provide learning materials and inputs that can develop students' English competence. ESP teachers need to struggle to make non-English major students hold a positive attitude toward English language learning. This finding showed that even though the students had confidence and motivation in learning English, they felt anxious and insecure during the teaching and learning process. Since this study involved non-English major students from different educational backgrounds, it was found that students' language learning strategies were various. The results did not show certain strategies used by the students in learning English in higher education. ESP teachers should provide a variety of teaching techniques that can help students maximize their English language learning.

Keywords: Attitudes; Learning strategies; Needs; Language learning strategies, IPER, Pharmacy/industrial pharmacy faculty students

Introduction

English has increasingly become significant in today's global era. It influences all aspects of human life such as science, health, pharmaceutical direction, education, trade, technology, etc. Thus, English language learners had better improve their English proficiency so that they can use English for communication with foreigners, absorb abundant information from reading various English texts, attain more knowledge to support academic performance, and develop self-potential to achieve success in a career.

Meanwhile, being proficient in English is not easy. English language learners will encounter many problems and challenges in learning English especially for those who learn English as a foreign language. Linguists identify a number of factors that limit the efficacy of English language instruction and learning in an EFL context, including cultural considerations, classroom variables like class size and time, teacher English proficiency, assessment, a dearth of vocabulary mastery, and ignorance of the true educational needs of the students. In addition, scholars state that students' previous learning experiences influence their current English proficiency. Students can be demotivated in learning English because of their displeasing experiences. Most EFL learners take part as non-English majors in higher education.

Nevertheless, they must take English courses as an educational requirement to finish their study. In other words, students learn English with different educational backgrounds at institute level. The English course, which is offered by the institute has some purposes such as English for General Purposes (EGP), English for Academic Purposes (EAP), and English for Specific Purposes (ESP). Some faculties prefer providing ESP courses. Five goals for teaching ESP are listed by Basturkmen (2010). These goals are to disclose language use in subject knowledge, create target performance competencies, educate underlying information, establish strategic competence, and nurture critical awareness. Teachers of ESP courses should be able to link students' background to the teaching materials in order to meet the students' needs. Through this course, students can get the opportunity to develop their English language competence for their future professional needs.

Considering non-English major students' needs in ESP teaching is very necessary. It should cover not only academic study needs but also pharmaceutical workplace related learning needs. Scholars found that students needed the materials relevant to their study. They also needed to improve their speaking and reading skills for their future career. Besides, they

took English courses for certain goals such as developing a career, finishing study and widening international relationships. Unfortunately, students had poor and low motivation towards the English program because English is taught with some assumptions from the teachers rather than based on the students' needs analysis. Whereas needs should be seen as an indispensable aspect of syllabus and module design. As a result, students have difficulties in school and college English learning content. Therefore, doing needs analysis is very beneficial to provide suitable English course materials for non-English major students.

Furthermore, the attitude of the students is crucial for maximizing learning and teaching outcomes. As a collection of attitudes on language use and its place in society, learners' attitudes can be categorized. Meanwhile, Mamun, et al. (2012) further affirm that specifically, linguistic behavior is explained by a concept called attitude toward language. It is undeniable that learning attitude influences students' academic performance. Latif, et al. (2011) found that attitude has a beneficial effect on performance in the English course. It reveals that there is a strong relationship between attitude and students' English achievement. However, having a positive attitude towards English language learning doesn't guarantee that students actively engage in the learning process. Teachers claim that even though the vast majority of the college students had positive attitudes in English language learning in general, they had negative attitudes to college language courses. This condition may be brought on by unfavorable emotions or dread related to the learning process in the classroom. Hence, ESP teachers are suggested to create an effective learning atmosphere and engage students in an active learning environment.

Moreover, ESP teachers need to be aware of learning strategies used by non-English major students so that they can adjust their teaching strategies that can be used to help the students succeed in learning English in higher education. Nowadays, English language learning aims to be more self-directed and learner-centered. To meet the new demands of the curriculum, students at tertiary level need to be adequately aware of learning strategies. According to scholars, students' language learning techniques significantly influenced their level of English proficiency.

From the explanation above, this study mainly focused on analyzing non English major students' needs, attitudes, and English language learning strategies. The results of the study can be the reference for ESP teachers to design ESP courses relevant to the students' needs.

Teachers are also encouraged to bring the opportunities for the students to have a positive attitude toward English language learning and develop effective teaching practice to accommodate students to maximize their language learning strategies. Therefore, ESP learning in higher education can meet students' future professional needs.

Literature review

Students needs in higher education

Hutchinson and Waters (1987) advocated the utilization of three comprehensive subcategories of needs during the process of needs analysis in language educational settings. Necessities: The linguistic abilities and knowledge that learners must possess in order to effectively operate within a specific context. Wants: Examination of learners' self-perception about knowledge requirements. While there may be variations in individual preferences and these preferences may be influenced by the perceived requirements of course designers, it is important to acknowledge that learners' preferences have an impact on the effectiveness of learning and so warrant consideration. The lack lies in the disparity between the desired level of language proficiency that learners aim to achieve and their current level of proficiency. The lack refers to the skills that learners consider as inadequate.

Based on the three classifications of needs, the teachers might examine the needs, wants and necessities in the level of higher education. According to linguists, students' needs are not only required English communication skills for performance duties, but also the performance skills that could help increase students' motivation for learning English and prepare the students' future jobs as being the target situation where English is going to be used, for example, making an appointment, contract and correspondence. Moreover, students are required to increase English language proficiency for students to use English and communicate meaning in spoken and written context at their institutes.

Some researchers confirmed that students' needs in higher levels included language skills and learning preferences. Teachers state that reading activities are the most preferred and deployed in the class, while speaking and listening are mostly preferred by students. However, the perceptions of the needs of students and teachers are significant discrepancies, especially students of higher education. The teachers could determine the students' needs and challenges by analyzing students' needs. Need analysis in higher education could be used in determining the language course. According to linguists, needs analysis findings will help the

ESP instructor find important data about the students. The instructor will be aware of their potential language-related professional needs, language-related needs, and language-related shortcomings. Liu, Chang, Yang, and Sun (2011) points out that need analysis could be hierarchical levels for instructional curriculum development. In addition, Brown (1995) needs analysis collected by subjective and objective information to construct and validate the curriculum instructions that fulfil the language learning requirement of students in the particular institution.

Language learning attitudes. An important component affecting language performance is attitude. Attitudes could construct linguistic behavior in particular and lead to consistent behavior. Learning behaviors and performance are both impacted by learners' attitudes. A significant correlation between attitude and success has also been shown in numerous studies on language attitudes. According to Mamun, et al. (2012), the respondents' good attitudes toward the English language can be linked to the fact that they were instrumentally motivated to learn the language.

Based on the previous studies, a positive attitude or negative attitude brings success and failure in learning English. According to Yosinta (2020), these attitudes could influence students' behavior toward English learning. In this case, the positive attitudes to English tend to desire and optimistic feelings to learn English that can give a positive impact on English achievement, while negative attitudes tend to feel stress and anxiety that can bring failure in learning English.

In the context of the classroom, attitudes toward the learning setting are acknowledged as a key determinant of the learning process and final success. However, because most students from non-English majors felt uncomfortable or were afraid of following instructions in class, they did not actively participate in the learning process. In addition, Noora (2018) discovered that the vast majority of these students enroll in college English classes merely because it is a requirement for admission to every institute. In other words, people see language learning positively overall but negatively toward college-level language courses. Based on their exposure and experiences in the academic settings and work field can encourage students' attitudes towards English language.

English Language Learning Strategies. Language learning techniques are viewed as deliberate choices made by students to speed up language acquisition. Additionally, Cohen

(1998) claimed that language learning strategies are the process that students selected to take actions in learning second or foreign languages through direct strategies and indirect strategies. There are two categories of language acquisition strategies: direct strategies and indirect strategies, according to Oxford.

Figure 1. Learning Strategies (adapted from Oxford, 1990)

According to Cheng et al. (2007), engineering students prefer to use cognitive techniques more often than social affective strategies. Surprisingly, metacognitive strategies are also rarely used. Their learning preferences, learning style, and the social environment in which they are learning English as a foreign language all have a significant role in how they choose particular learning tactics. They also firmly believed that such strategies would benefit English language learning. Their limited learning objectives include meeting emotional requirements, increasing score increases, improving reading and listening comprehension, and last but not least, memorization of words and phrases.

Method

Research design

This study used a descriptive study aimed at describing non-English major students' needs, attitudes, and learning strategies towards their English language learning at institute level. To collect the descriptive data, this study used a survey method with a cross-sectional design. Creswell (2005) explains that a cross-sectional design is used when the researchers collect the data at one point in time. In addition, Mathers, Fox and Hunn (2009) state that cross sectional survey provides a snapshot of what is happening in a group at particular time.

The survey was developed by using Google Form and the link was shared among students via telegram.

Sampling method

This study was conducted at one of institutes in Uzbekistan for a bachelor's program. There are 3 directions (Pharmacy, industrial pharmacy, medical care). However, the English education study program was excluded since the population of this study was non-English major students at the institute.

In choosing the sample, this study used non random sampling - convenience or opportunistic sampling. This sampling is defined as a sampling technique in which the respondents are selected purely because they are easily accessible. It means that all non-English major students at the institute were possible to be the sample of this study. However, the researchers limited the number of the sample. There were 200 students involved in this study. The participants comprised female students (50%) and female students (50%). The distribution of the sample of this study is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1

Sample of the study.

N o	Faculty	Study Program	Number of Student s	Percenta ge
1	Faculty of Pharmacy	Pharmaceutical issues (by types)	100	50%
2	Faculty of Medical care	Medical care (by types)	100	50%
		Total	180	100

Questionnaire is the common instrument used for a descriptive survey study. There were three kinds of questionnaires used in this study: (1) students' needs questionnaire, (2) learning attitude questionnaire, and (3) language learning strategies questionnaire.

Data collection

There were some procedures in conducting this study. First, researchers identified problems of the study. It was found that English was taught based on ESP teachers' preferences and the lens of their teaching experiences without considering non-English students' needs, attitude, and English language learning strategies. Second, the instruments were developed based on the purposes of this study. There were three kinds of questionnaires used in this study: (1) students' needs analysis questionnaire, (2) learning attitude questionnaire, and (3) English language learning strategies questionnaire.

Before the instruments were given to the sample, they had been translated into Indonesian since the respondents of this study were non-English major students. Third, researchers organized the instruments using Google Form to make it easier accessed by the students. Fourth, researchers arranged the research schedule and determined the sample. They coordinated with the practical teachers from 3 study programs of the institute. Fifth, researchers collected the data by sharing the link of the Google Form to the practical teachers. Then, the practical teachers distributed the link to their students via telegram. Since 17 out of 210 of the responses were not completely filled in by the students, there were 200 responses that were analyzed by researchers.

Questionnaire is the common instrument used for a descriptive survey study. There were three kinds of questionnaires used in this study: (1) students' needs questionnaire, (2) learning attitude questionnaire, and (3) language learning strategies questionnaire.

Students' needs questionnaire

The needs analysis survey gathered participants' basic characteristics, such as their gender, academic programmes, semester, and occupation. Meanwhile, the students' needs questionnaire used in this study was developed by using eight aspects from a complete model of needs analysis in ESP proposed by Dudley-Evans and ST John (1998), Xing (2018), and Wu and Lou (2018). There were 28 items of the questionnaire consisting of professional information, personal information, English language information, learners' lacks, language learning information, target situation, learners' needs from the course, and learning environment.

Learning attitude questionnaire

To investigate non-English major students' learning attitude, this study used a language learning attitude questionnaire written by Orwig (1995) from SIL International. There were 36 statements distributed to students consisting of 6 aspects measured: self-image, inhibition, risk-taking, ego permeability, motivation, and ambiguity.

Language learning strategies questionnaire

This study used a questionnaire of Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) Version 7.0 (ESL/EFL) from Oxford (1989). There were 50 statements in form of Likert Scale consisting of six learning strategies: memory, cognitive, compensation, metacognitive, affective, and social.

Data analysis

Data analysis is deployed by using descriptive analysis to answer research questions. The researchers administered the needs analysis questionnaire, learning attitudes questionnaire and language learning strategies questionnaire. Then, the students' responses to the questionnaires were analyzed using percentage analysis to classify students' needs, learning attitudes, and language learning strategies. The highest percentage of the answers of each question is considered representing students' needs, attitudes, and learning strategies. The tables are used to display the results and data results were presented descriptively.

Findings

Findings and discussion section is where you report the results of your study based upon the methodology you applied to obtain significant information regarding your research focus. This section should state the findings of the research arranged in a logical sequence without any bias interpretation. The discussion will always connect to the introduction by ways of the research questions you have posed and the theories or literature you reviewed, but it does not simply reiterate or rearrange the introduction; the discussion should always explain how your study has relocated the readers' understanding of the research questions or problems from where you left them at the end of the introduction section.

Results of students' needs analysis

Professional information about the learners

There were (61.7%) students strongly agreed that learning English inside and outside

the class can help their education and career while (37.8%) students agreed, and (0.5%) students moderate. No student disagreed and strongly disagreed with this statement.

Personal information about the learners

Students considered the importance of learning English at the institute level for different reasons. 43.3% of the students thought that learning English could support the success of their future career. 37.2% of the students learned English because it helped them communicate with foreigners. 16.1% of the students agreed that learning English could support the success of their study. While only a few students learned English for other reasons such as determining graduation (2.2%), learning international language (0.5%), and increasing vocabulary about the field of study (0.5%).

English language information about the learners

This aspect investigated students' current skill (listening, speaking, reading, and writing) and language use (vocabulary, grammar, pronunciation). Students admitted that they had average ability for reading (48%), vocabulary (44%), grammar (43%), and pronunciation (47%) while they considered that their listening (41%), speaking (49%), and listening (47%) abilities were in good level. The results are illustrated in the following diagram.

Figure 2. Students' current skill and language use

For the English proficiency level, there were 44 students (24%) in lower basic level, 67 students (37%) in upper basic level, 48 students (27%) in lower intermediate level, 21 students (12%) in upper intermediate, and no student was in advanced level.

The learners' lacks

After asking the learners to list skills and language uses from the hardest one, students answered that level of difficulty in learning English as follows: grammar (24%), listening (22%), pronunciation (20%), vocabulary (14%), speaking (13%), writing (4%), and reading (3%).

Language learning information

Students' answers for this aspect could be used to find effective ways of learning the skills and language use determined by the lack. The aspects used adapted the theory of Xing (2018) attempt to determine English course activities to obtain their weaknesses and strengths based on their preference activities. The information was about the students' preferences for learning activities to have input in order to increase their language skills including listening, speaking, reading, writing and supplementary language skills consisting of vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation. In summary, the students' preferences are a variety for each skill. The results for this aspect are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2

Language learning information.

N	ASPECT	ACTIVITIES	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
1	Listening activity that the students like	identify things related to dialog/monologue	74	41,1%
		identify expressions related to dialog/monologue	43	23,9%
		answer questions in written from dialog/monologue	32	17,8%
		answer questions orally from dialog/monologue	31	17,2%
2	Speaking	discuss certain topic or problem	65	36,1%
		pronunciation and intonation		
		discuss the content of the text in group to comprehend it	42	23,3%

		read the text individually and answer questions about the text	29	16,1%
		analyze new vocabulary	6	3,3%
4	Writing activity that the students like	arrange sentences into one correct paragraph	99	55%
		identify and correct sentence structure errors	39	21,7%
		write the text that is similar to the text given	25	13,9%
		identify and correct punctuation errors in the text	17	9,4%
5	Learning activity that	match English words or expressions with provided meanings	80	44,4%
	mastery	match English words or expressions with pictures, solving Kahoot tests	27	15%
		complete sentences or paragraphs using own words based on knowledge	23	12,8%
		complete sentences or paragraphs with the words given	22	12,2%
6	Learning activity that	write sentences based on patterns that have been learned	69	38,3%
	can improve	identify sentence structure errors	60	33,3%
	the students' grammar mastery	justify sentence structure errors	51	28,3%
7	Learning activity that	imitate the pronunciation exemplified by the practical teacher	100	55,6%
	can improve	discuss with classmate or small group about the correct pronunciation	43	23,9%
	the			%

students' pronunciation on	read aloud by looking at the phonetic transcription	33	18,3 %
	praticice English pronunciation by having dialogue in English	1	0.5%
	watch DVD	1	0.5%

Target situation

The aspects of the situation analysis questionnaire are adapted from the theory Wu and Lou (2018). Target situation presents the expectation of English used in future works. There are two aspects showing the activities of students in their future pharmacy careers based on their necessities. The information about how language use and skills are used in the target situation. From the questionnaire results, it was revealed that the interaction using English with the clients and customers are needed to accommodate their future careers. Besides their priorities, written English and read English texts had chosen to support their pharmacy career in the target situation.

Therefore, communicative skills using English are necessary to learn at present for future time. Communication in written and spoken English are crucial to support their careers in any work field. As a consequence, the teachers and stakeholders should consider the demands in the work field.

Table 3

Target situation.

N	ASPECT	ACTIVITI	TOTA	PERCENTA
o		ES	L	GE
1	English subject is supposed to make students	interact using spoken English well at worklater understand what is delivered by client orboss from abroad at work later use sentence structure (grammar) well interact using written English well at worklater understand texts related to work later	128 71 50 48 38	71,1% 39,4% 27,8% 26,7% 21,1%

	master vocabulary related to the expertise area	36	20%
Students will use English more often to ... at work later	interact using spoken English with clients or customers	112	62,2%
	read English texts to expand work skill	32	17,8%
	join job training and international seminar	22	12,2%
	interact using both formal and informal written English (correspondence)	13	7,2%
	interact using both spoken and written English with clients and boss	1	0.5%

Learners' needs from the course

This aspect contains information about what is wanted by the learners from their English class. For the learning topic, most students prefer to have learning materials related to daily life, their field of study, and education. Only a few students like the learning topic about current issues and hobbies. The summary of the results is displayed in the following diagram.

Figure 3. Pharmacy/industrial pharmacy, medical care students' learning topic preferences

Meanwhile, most students have interest in learning general vocabulary that can be used in daily life (71,7%). While the others (28,3%) prefer the medical and pharmaceutical terms or vocabulary related to the field of study. The same result also happens to the learning of grammar. 86% of the students are interested in learning grammar that can be used for general communication and 14% prefer learning grammar about scientific discourse related to their field of study. In addition, most students (90,6%) realized the importance of learning English pronunciation. Furthermore, students expect some learning inputs that they need from the course. The results are summed up in Table 4 below.

Table 4

Learning input.

N	ASPECT	LEARNING INPUT	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE
1	Listening	listen to the lecturer or instructor	87	48,3%
		listen to the presentation or discussion of national and international seminar	70	38,9%
		listen to authentic materials such as news, radio broadcasting, film, and song	69	38,3%
		comprehend test (CEFR, examination, etc)	63	35%
		daily conversation	1	0.5%
		monolog and dialog that provide list of new vocabulary and phonetic transcription	100	55,6%
2	Speaking	monolog and dialog that provide pictures commonly used authentic materials	62	34,4%
		monolog and dialog	34	18,9%
		monolog and dialog	25	13,9%
		monolog and dialog	25	13,9%
3	Reading	read textbook	82	45,6%
		read English information from internet	58	32,2%
		read assignment	57	31,7%
		read journal / academic publication	46	25,6%
		read manual or product description	37	20,6%

	read office documents such as letters or contract documents	31	17,2%
	read instructions, rules and notes in the lab	27	15%
4	Writing		
	write report or assignment	64	35,6%
	write scientific articles, papers, proposals	57	31,7%
	answer written examination	48	26,7%
	write duties at work (memo, correspondence)	41	22,8%
	write job application letter	38	21,1%
	write instructions (messages, direction)	38	21,1%
	write resume	31	17,2%
	describe product	28	15,6%
	describe diagram, table, chart	18	10%

Learning environment

This analysis tells the information about the environment in which the course will be run. In the process of learning English, students prefer to work on assignments/learning activities in groups (43%), class discussion (47%), individually (16%), and in pairs (14%). Meanwhile, during the process of learning English in class, students would prefer to discuss problems or do assignments (61%) rather than writing all the information explained by the practical teacher (23%) and just listening to the lecturer's explanation in class (16%). Moreover, in doing English assignments in class, students prefer the practical teacher to give examples about certain discussions then give assignments (37%), provide questions then discuss them (33%), and observe students' work and then provide answers if students get difficulty (26%). Just a few of them (4%) like the practical teacher who goes around the class and gives comments on students' work.

Results of students' learning attitude

In general, non-English major students of this study had a negative attitude toward their English learning at institute level. They showed a positive attitude only for self-image and motivation while inhibition, risk taking, ego permeability, and ambiguity hold negative attitudes. Table 5 presents the result.

Table 5

Results of students' learning attitude.

N	ASPECT	MEAN	<u>POSITIVE</u>		<u>NEGATIVE</u>	
			<u>PERCENTAG</u>	<u>TOTAL</u>	<u>PERCENTAG</u>	<u>E</u>
1	Self- Image	1.2	81	45%	99	55%
2	Inhibition	-	26	14.0%	154	86%
3	Risk-taking	-1.05	11	6%	169	97%
4	Ego Permeability	-0.06	45	25%	135	75%
5	Motivation	2	107	59%	73	41%
6	Ambiguity	-	23	13%	157	87%
		0.2				

Results of students' language learning strategies

The result from language learning strategies questionnaire indicated that non- English major students of this study used different kinds of English language learning strategies: 1) Metacognitive (58,6%), 2) Memory (52,5%), 3) Affective (51%), 4) Social (49,3%), 5) Compensation (47,6%), and 6) Cognitive (44,1%). The results can be seen in Table 6 below.

Table 6Results of students' language learning strategies.

NO	STRATEGIE	NEVE	SELDO	SOMETIM	USUALL	ALWA
	S	R	M	ES	Y	YS
1	Memory	3,5%	11,7%	32.3%	35.7%	16.8%
			15,2%		52,5%	
2	Cognitive	5,5%	14,7%	35.7%	31,5%	12,6%

		20,2			44,1
		%			%
3	Compensation	8,2%	13%	31.2%	35,3% 12,3%
		21,2			47,6
		%			%
4	Metacognitive	3%	8,6%	29.8%	31,7% 26,9%
		11,6			58,6
		%			%
5	Affective	9,8%	10,8%	28.4%	30,4% 20,6%
		20,6			51%
		%			%
6	Social	6,7%	14,1%	29.9%	31,8% 17,5%
		20,8			49,3
		%			%

Discussion

The results of the study reveal some important points related to non-English major students' needs, learning attitude, and English language learning strategies. First, English is taught for the students from different educational backgrounds in higher education to help students succeed both in education and their future career.

Second, most non-English major students in this study had average and good ability for the English skills and language use. Meanwhile, their English proficiency level was in the upper basic level. Chostelidou (2010) states that students' previous learning experiences influence their current English proficiency. It indicated that students had not maximally achieved the learning objectives from the previous English course yet.

Third, students still lacked all English skills and language use. Therefore, ESP teachers should provide learning materials and inputs that can develop students' English competence. For the learning materials, students' learning preference is about the topic of daily life and field of their study. Budianto (2004) affirms that students needed the materials relevant to their study. Students could engage more in the learning process when they are familiar with the topic discussed. For the learning inputs, students need more learning activities that can direct them to be independent learners. According to Septiana, Petrus & Inderawati (2020), the expected

activities based on students' needs could lead to the successful English achievement of students. Hence, ESP teachers should provide opportunities for the students to explore and practice more on their English mastery.

Fourth, students prefer to have collaborative learning during the study and discuss the materials by using the examples from the real contexts. This finding reveals that contextual teaching and learning can benefit non-English major students to comprehend more the topic so that they can use English to support their future professional needs.

Fifth, ESP teachers need to struggle to make non-English major students hold a positive attitude toward English language learning. This study reveals that even though the students had confidence and motivation in learning English, they feel anxious and insecure during the teaching and learning process. ESP teachers need to create an effective learning atmosphere and engage students in an active learning environment to bring the opportunities for the students to have a positive attitude toward English language learning as Latifah et al. (2011) found that attitude plays a positive impact on performance in the English course.

Sixth, since this study involved non-English major students from different educational backgrounds, it was found that students' language learning strategies were various. The results did not show certain strategies used by the students in learning English in higher education. Meanwhile, Ilma (2014) found that students' language learning strategies made a significant contribution to their English proficiency. Therefore, ESP teachers should provide a variety of teaching techniques that can help students maximize their English language learning.

Conclusion. After conducting a survey about non-English major pharmacy students' needs, attitude, and English language learning strategies, the results show that English teachers need to design ESP courses relevant to the students' needs. The course should cover not only academic needs but also workplace related learning needs on the basis of students' needs analysis not on the basis of the teachers' intuition and assumptions. Moreover, most non-English major students still hold a negative attitude toward English language learning. ESP teachers need to create an effective learning atmosphere and engage students in an active learning environment to bring the opportunities for the students to have a positive attitude toward English language learning. Furthermore, ESP teachers need to adjust their teaching strategies with language learning strategies used by non-English major students. Since students employed various strategies in learning English. In short, ESP teachers must fit their teaching practice with the

students' needs and conditions.

Considering the results of this study, researchers proposed some suggestions. First, English is taught to the students with different educational backgrounds in higher education. Hence, ESP teachers need to do needs analysis to select appropriate teaching materials and activities before designing their ESP class. Teachers need to realize that they should accommodate their teaching practice optimally to help non-English major students achieve their learning objectives. Second, ESP teachers need to create an effective learning atmosphere and engage students in an active learning environment to bring the opportunities for the students to have a positive attitude toward English language learning. Third, ESP teachers are demanded to develop effective teaching practice to accommodate students and maximize their language learning strategies. Fourth, students at institute level need to learn English to support their success both in education and future professional pharmaceutical and medical needs. They have to be aware of their attitude and strategies in learning English to help them direct their own learning.

References

1. Ahmed, S. (2015). Attitudes towards English language learning among EFL learners at UMSKAL. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(18), 6-16.
2. Xalmurzayevna, Y. S., Eshmanov, G., & Zairjanovich, Y. S. (2021). СЕКЦІЯ XVIII. ФІЛОЛОГІЯ ТА ЖУРНАЛІСТИКА. ТРАДИЦІЙНІ ТА ІННОВАЦІЙНІ ПІДХОДИ ДО НАУКОВИХ ДОСЛІДЖЕНЬ, 122.
3. XALMURZAYEVNA, Y. S., & ZAIRJANOVICH, Y. S. (2020, June). PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF WRITTEN ADVERTISEMENTS FROM UZBEK NEWSPAPERS AND MAGAZINES. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 21-24).
4. Yuldashev, S. Z. (2021). MERITS AND DEMERITS OF ONLINE EDUCATION IN TRAINING COURSES (ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHER'S COURSE). *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(CSPI conference 2), 546-553.
5. XALMURZAYEVNA, Y. S., & ZAIRJANOVICH, Y. S. (2021, January). MODERN TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING LISTENING. In *Archive of Conferences* (pp. 3-4).
6. Yuldasheva, S., Eshmanov, G. A., Yuldashev, S., & Xidirova, M. (2021). TEACHING VOCABULARY-THE BASIS FOR FORMING FOUR MAIN SKILLS (LISTENING,

SPEAKING, READING AND WRITING). Матеріали конференцій МЦНД.

7. Karimovich, S. S., Khalmurzayevna, Y. S., & Zairjanovich, Y. S. (2022, September). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF GAME-BASED LEARNING FOR TEACHING ENGLISH TO IPER (THE INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH) PHARMACY STUDENTS. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION" (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 20-32).

8. Xalmurzayevna, Y. S., Karimovich, S. S., & Zairjanovich, Y. S. (2021, April). HYBRID TEACHING STRATEGIES TO OPTIMIZE LEARNING SPACES. In Archive of Conferences (Vol. 19, No. 1, pp. 5-7).

9. Xalmurzayevna, Y. S., Karimovich, S. S., Zairjanovich, Y. S., & Qizi, X. M. I. (2021, June). IMPORTANCE OF ONLINE ASSESSMENT IN THE E-LEARNING PROCESS. In Archive of Conferences (Vol. 27, No. 1, pp. 16-17).

10. Xalmurzayevna, Y. S., Karimovich, S. S., Zairjanovich, Y. S., & Qizi, X. M. I. (2021, June). THE EFFECTIVENESS OF QUIZLET APPLICATION TOWARDS STUDENTS'MOTIVATION IN LEARNING VOCABULARY. In Archive of Conferences (Vol. 26, No. 1, pp. 16-18).

11. Xalmurzayevna, Y. S., Eshmanov, G., Zairjanovich, Y. S., & Qizi, X. M. I. (2021). THE USAGE OF GROUP WORK IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS. Conferencious Online, 86-88.

12. YULDASHEV, S. Z., & YULDASHEVA, S. X. (2022). LEARNERS' ATTITUDES IN LEARNING ENGLISH FOR TOURISM USING GOOGLE CLASSROOM IN TASHKENT TOURISM COLLEGE. Development and innovations in science, 1(1), 93-100.

13. Zairjanovich, Y. S., & Xalmurzayevna, Y. S. (2022, February). TEACHING ENGLISH FOR TOURISM STUDENTS (ESP AND E-LEARNING). In Archive of Conferences (pp. 8-10).

14. Xalmurzayevna, Y. S., Karimovich, S. S., Zairjanovich, Y. S., & Qizi, X. M. I. (2021, June). HYBRID TEACHING AND LEARNING TIPS FOR Teachers. In Archive of Conferences (Vol. 28, No. 1, pp. 12-14).

15. Mahamadali Turdaliyevich Toshxonov, Sherzod Zairjanovich Yuldashev. (2022, October) THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ISSUES OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE "THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS

16. Shakabil Karimovich Shayakubov, Saodat Khalmurzayevna Yuldasheva, Sherzod Zairjanovich Yuldashev, Dilnoza Anvarovna Akhmedova. (2022, 5 November) THE ROLE OF ASSESSMENT ON ENGLISH FOR THE INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH. INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE " INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION"

17. Saodat Khalmurzayevna Yuldasheva, Mahamadali Turdaliyevich Toshxonov, Sherzod Zairjanovich Yuldashev. (2022, 3 January) USING MOBILE APPS FOR TEACHING ESL&EFL IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS. Vol. 2 No. 8 (2023): YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS

18. Khalmurzayevna, Y. S., Nuritdinovich, F. S., & Karimovich, S. S. (2023). RISK ASSESSMENT OF THE INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM AND THE APPLICATION OF AUDITING PROCEDURES IN AUDIT OF ENVIRONMENTAL COSTS. International Journal Of Management And Economics Fundamental, 3(05), 15-27.

19. Yuldasheva Saodat Khalmurzayevna, Ganiev Shakhridin Vakhidovich, Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich (2023/6/9). 21st Century Modern English Teacher's Professional Competences. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 8-13

20. Yuldasheva Saodat Khalmurzayevna, Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich (2023/9/20) The Perspectives of English Teachers' Pedagogic Competence In Teaching English Through Online and Offline Tools. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 111-121

21. Ismailov Kamolatdin Kurultaevich, Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich, Sadikova Dildor Abdullayevna, Talipov Begzod Botirovich, Taryanikova Marina Anatolievna (2023/10/23). Specifics Of Teaching Foreign Language Speaking To Students At A Non-Linguistic Institute (Iper) In The Distance Learning Format. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 549-559

22. Alisherovna R. N. FUNCTIONAL ANALYSIS OF TEXTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEKI //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 1. – С. 185-187.
23. Yuldasheva Saodat Khalmurzayevna, Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich (2023/11/12). Overthrown Barriers In Teaching Efl To Non-Linguistic Students (Iper Students). Gospodarka i Innowacje, 123-132
24. Talipov Begzod Botirovich, Akhmedova Dilnoza Anvarovna, Toshkhonov Mahamadali Turdaliyevich. (2023, 2 January) THE DEVELOPMENT OF PBL TEACHING METHOD FOR TEACHING PRACTICAL ENGLISH IN IPER (INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH) “INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE " INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION"
25. Akhmedova Dilnoza Anvarovna. (2023, 23 January) Strategies for Increasing Awareness of Pharmaceutical Students' Divergences. Miasto Przyszłości 31, 277-280
26. Talipov Begzod Botirovich, Akhmedova Dilnoza Anvarovna, Toshkhonov Mahamadali Turdaliyevich. (2023, 31 January) ESP AND STUDENTS' NEEDS IN LEARNING ENGLISH FOR PHARMACY. “INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH”
27. Akhmedova Dilnoza Anvarovna, Tolipov Begzod Batirovich. (2023, 28 January) EFFECTIVENESS OF INTEGRATING PROJECT-BASED LEARNING INTO ESP COURSES FOR IMPROVING ESP TEACHING TO IPER (THE INSTITUTE OF PHARMACEUTICAL EDUCATION AND RESEARCH) PHARMACY STUDENTS “Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal”
28. Дильдор Абдуллаевна Садыкова (2022/10/17) МЕСТО ЛЕКСИКИ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ РУССКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 387-390
29. Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich. ENGLISH AND SUBJECT INTEGRATION IN MATHEMATICS AND GEOGRAPHY. Zbiór artykułów naukowych recenzowanych. 201 pp
30. Yuldasheva Saodat Khalmurzayevna, Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich (2023/12/22). OPPORTUNITIES FOR DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF

PHARMACEUTICAL INSTITUTE STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE. Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 148-153 pp

31. Yuldasheva Saodat Khalmurzayevna, Yuldashev Sherzod Zairjanovich (2024/01/19)Conformation Of the Foreign Language Competence of Pharmacy and Industrial Pharmacy Students (IPER). Best Journal of Innovation in Science, Research and Development, 304-312 pp